

On the Limited Applicability of Kostanecki's Reaction.

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In a series of papers Heilbron and his co-workers (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 1263; 1934, 1311, 1581; 1935, 296; *cf.* also Wittig, Baugert and Richter, *Annalen*, 1925, 446, 155; Bargellini, *Atti. R. Accad. Lincei*, 1925, 2, 261; Baker and Eastwood, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 2906; Chadha, Mahal and Venkataraman, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 1460; Flynn and Robertson, *ibid.*, 1936, 215) have shown that the course of Kostanecki's reaction is uncertain in as much as both coumarins and chromones are formed in this reaction (as in Simonis' reaction) and the reaction is dependent not only on the acid anhydrides and the salt used but also on the nature of the *o*-hydroxyphenylketone.

4-Chloro-2-aceto-1-naphthol and 4-chloro-2-propio-1-naphthol, prepared by heating the crude acetyl or propionyl derivative of 4-chloro-1-naphthol with aluminium chloride (Fries' rearrangement), have been submitted to Kostanecki's reaction with the typical acid anhydrides and their sodium salts, *e.g.*, (A) sodium acetate and acetic anhydride, (B) sodium propionate and propionic anhydride (C) sodium phenylacetate and phenylacetic anhydride, and (D) sodium benzoate and benzoic anhydride.

(A) On heating with sodium acetate and acetic anhydride both aceto- and propionaphthols give chromones and coumarins are not formed. In the case of 4-chloro-2-aceto-1-naphthol the 3-acetyl derivative of 6-chloro-2-methyl-1:4- $\alpha\beta$ -naphthopyrone and in the case

of 4-chloro-2-propio-1-naphthol, 6-chloro-2:3-dimethyl-1:4- $\alpha\beta$ -naphthapyrone is formed, which is identical with the condensation product of 4-chloro-1-naphthol and methyl acetoacetic ester in presence of phosphorus pentoxide (Chakravarti and Bagchi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **13**, 649), as is shown by mixed melting point and the formation of identical benzylidene derivative.

(B) With sodium propionate and propionic anhydride, however, 4-chloro-2-aceto-1-naphthol gives a coumarin, e.g., 6-chloro-3:4-dimethyl-1:2- $\alpha\beta$ -naphthapyrone. It is identical, as proved by mixed melting point, with the product obtained by condensing 4-chloro-1-naphthol with methyl-acetoacetic ester using sulphuric acid as the condensing agent (Chakravarti and Bagchi, *loc. cit.*). 4-Chloro-2-

propio-1-naphthol also gives a coumarin (6-chloro-3-methyl-4-ethyl-1:2- $\alpha\beta$ -naphthapyrone) when heated with propionic anhydride and

sodium propionate. This compound does not form a benzylidene derivative.

(C) Using phenylacetic anhydride and sodium phenylacetate, 4-chloro-2-aceto-1-naphthol yields 6-chloro-4-methyl-3-phenyl-1:2- $\alpha\beta$ -naphthapyrone, which is identical with the condensation product of 4-chloro-1-naphthol and phenyl-acetoacetic ester using sulphuric acid as the condensing agent (Chakravarti and Bagchi, *loc. cit.*).

(D) When 4-chloro-2-aceto-1-naphthol is heated with benzoic anhydride and sodium benzoate, 6-chloro-2-phenyl-3-benzoyl-1:4- $\alpha\beta$ -naphthapyrone is obtained as the main product, only traces of a second substance could be isolated which is probably the non-benzoylated 1:4- $\alpha\beta$ -naphthapyrone.

The results obtained are, therefore, in agreement with the observations of Heilbron and co-workers (*loc. cit.*).

The simplest chromone from 4-chloro-2-aceto-1-naphthol, *e.g.*, 6-chloro-1:4- $\alpha\beta$ -naphthapyrone has also been obtained by condensing it with ethyl formate in presence of molecular sodium. The intermediate hydroxymethylene-2-aceto-4-chloro-1-naphthol is a very stable compound and forms a characteristic green copper salt and yields a pyrazole derivative, 1-phenyl-3 (4'-chloro-1'-oxy-)- β -naphthylpyrazole with phenylhydrazine.

Various chalcones have been obtained by reacting 4-chloro-2-aceto-1-naphthol with different aldehydes, *e.g.*, benzaldehyde, anisaldehyde and veratric aldehyde. The insolubility of these chalcones in caustic alkalies and the fact that they are obtained as insoluble derivatives even in alkaline medium, when 4-chloro-2-aceto-1-naphthol is condensed with the aldehydes in presence of alcoholic sodium ethoxide led us to think that they are flavanone derivatives, but they do not respond to the colour test usually given by the flavanones (*cf.* Ashahiua, Shinoda and Inubuse, *J. Pharm. Soc. Japan*, 1928, **48**, 208; Ashahina and Inubuse, *Ber.*, 1928, **61**, 1646; Kuroda, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 755). Attempts to prepare flavanones from these chalcones by boiling them with alcoholic sulphuric acid have not been successful, as pure products cannot be obtained.

4-Bromo-2-aceto-1-naphthol, prepared from 4-bromo-1-naphthol by Fries' rearrangement, is found to be identical with the compound obtained by Torry (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, **31**, 1322) by bromination of 2-aceto-1-naphthol as is proved by the mixed melting point and the identical benzylidene derivative (m.p. 177°). Torry did not supply any definite evidence in favour of the assigned position of the bromine atom, but the present method of the preparation of the ketone from 4-bromo-1-naphthol leaves no doubt about the position of the bromine atom. Like acetochloronaphthol, 4-bromo-2-aceto-1-naphthol condenses with ethyl formate to give a stable hydroxymethylene compound which forms a pyrazole, e.g., 1-phenyl-3-(4'-bromo-1'-oxy)- β -naphthylpyrazole, with phenylhydrazine in acetic acid solution.

EXPERIMENTAL.

4-Chloro-2-aceto-1-naphthol (4-chloro-1-oxy- β -naphthylmethyl ketone).—Crude acetyl 4-chloro-1-naphthol, obtained from 4-chloro-1-naphthol (5 g.) and acetyl chloride (3.5 g.), was treated with finely powdered aluminium chloride (7 g.) and the mixture heated for 1½ hours on the water-bath. The cold mass was treated with ice and concentrated hydrochloric acid and again heated on a water-bath for 1 hour. The separated solid was collected, washed with water and crystallised as greenish needles from rectified spirit, m.p. 121°, yield 3.5 g. It gives a deep green colour with ferric chloride in alcoholic solution. It forms a very insoluble sodium salt and dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a reddish brown colour. (Found : Cl, 16.24. $C_{12}H_9O_2$ Cl requires Cl, 16.10 per cent).

The *phenylhydrazone* crystallised from rectified spirit, m.p. 158-59°. (Found : N, 9.31. $C_{18}H_{15}ON_2Cl$ requires N, 9.01 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* crystallised from dilute acetic acid, it does not melt up to 275°.

The *methyl ether*, prepared by the action of dimethyl sulphate on an alkaline solution of the ketone, crystallised from methyl alcohol as yellowish needles, m.p. 66-67°. (Found : OMe, 12.61. $C_{14}H_{11}O_2Cl$ requires OMe, 13.22 per cent).

The *benzoyl* derivative crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 123-24°. (Found : Cl, 11.32. $C_{19}H_{13}O_3$ Cl requires Cl, 10.94 per cent).

6-Chloro-2-methyl-3-acetyl-1 : 4- $\alpha\beta$ -naphthalipyronone.—A mixture of 4-chloro-2-aceto-1-naphthol (2 g.), acetic anhydride (8.5 g.) and freshly

fused sodium acetate (3.5 g.) was heated at 130-140° for 2 hours. The temperature was raised in course of 3 hours to 160-170° which was maintained for 4 hours more. The reaction mixture was cooled, treated with water and heated on a water-bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour and the solid was collected and extracted with alcohol. The alcoholic solution on cooling deposited a substance, m.p. 180-85°. On recrystallisation from glacial acetic acid almost colourless needles, m.p. 188-89°, were obtained. The substance, obtained from the acetic acid and alcohol mother-liquors by dilution with water, was subjected to repeated crystallisation from spirit but no second product could be isolated. (Found : C, 67.23 ; H, 3.85 ; Cl, 12.33. $C_{16}H_{11}O_3Cl$ requires C, 57.01 ; H, 3.84 ; Cl, 12.39 per cent).

6-Chloro-3 : 4-dimethyl-1 : 2- $\alpha\beta$ -naphthapyrone.—A mixture of 4-chloro-2-aceto-1-naphthol (2 g.), propionic anhydride (6.5 g.) and sodium propionate (2.5 g.) was heated at 130-140° for 1 hour. The temperature was raised to 190° in course of 2 hours and it was heated at this temperature for 3 hours more. The tarry reaction product was heated with 10% sodium carbonate solution for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour and the product washed with water and rectified spirit. It was finally extracted with boiling glacial acetic acid and the dirty substance, deposited on cooling, on repeated crystallisation from glacial acetic acid (charcoal) gave reddish needles, m.p. 202-3°, mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen of 6-chloro-3 : 4-dimethyl-1 : 2- $\alpha\beta$ -naphthapyrone, obtained by the condensation of 4-chloro-1-naphthol and methyl-acetoacetic ester with sulphuric acid as the condensing agent (Chakravarti and Bagchi, *loc. cit.*).

6-Chloro-2-phenyl-3-benzoyl-1 : 4- $\alpha\beta$ -naphthapyrone.—A mixture of 4-chloro-2-aceto-1-naphthol (2 g.), benzoic anhydride (10 g.) and sodium benzoate (4 g.) was heated at 130-140° for 1 $\frac{1}{2}$ hours and then at 190° for 6 hours. The mixture was heated on a water-bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour with 10% sodium carbonate solution and the product crystallised from glacial acetic acid (charcoal) as yellow needles, m.p. 224°. (Found : Cl, 8.37. $C_{26}H_{15}O_3$ Cl requires Cl, 8.65 per cent).

The precipitate, obtained by diluting the acetic acid mother liquor, was extracted with rectified spirit and on cooling a substance, m.p. 210-15°, was obtained, but it did not depress the m.p. of 6-chloro-2-phenyl-3-benzoyl-1 : 4- $\alpha\beta$ -naphthapyrone. The alcohol mother liquor on dilution gave a substance which after crystallisation from rectified spirit yielded a very small quantity of a substance, m.p. 152-54°.

6-Chloro-4-methyl-3-phenyl-1 : 2- α -naphthapyrone.—4-Chloro-2-aceto-1-naphthol (2 g.), phenylacetic anhydride (8 g.) and sodium phenylacetate (2.5 g.) were heated at 130-40° for 1½ hours and then at 180° for 6 hours. The product, isolated in the usual manner, crystallised from glacial acetic acid (charcoal) as pale yellow needles, m.p. 215-16°, mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of 6-chloro-4-methyl-3-phenyl-1 : 2- α -naphthapyrone, obtained by the condensation of 4-chloro-1-naphthol and α -phenyl-acetoacetic ester (Chakravarti and Bagchi, *loc. cit.*).

Hydroxymethylene-2-aceto-4-chloro-1-naphthol.—4-Chloro-2-aceto-1-naphthol (2.5 g.), suspended in dry formic ester (5.5 g.), was gradually added to a cold suspension of molecular sodium (1.5 g.) in dry ether (30 c.c.). The reaction set in after a few minutes and after keeping overnight the solution was treated with water, the ethereal layer was removed and the aqueous solution acidified. The yellow substance was collected and crystallised from rectified spirit as yellow amorphous powder, m.p. 146-47°. It gives a faint brown colour with ferric chloride and a green precipitate with copper acetate. (Found : Cl, 14.52. C₁₃H₉O₃ Cl requires Cl, 14.29 per cent).

1-Phenyl-3-(4'-chloro-1'-oxy)- β -naphthylpyrazole was obtained by heating the above hydroxymethylene ketone with phenylhydrazine in glacial acetic acid solution on a water-bath for 2 hours. The solution on adding water deposited a red tarry mass, which was washed with dilute alcohol and finally crystallised from dilute acetic acid (charcoal) as yellow needles, m.p. 184°. (Found : N, 8.89. C₁₉H₁₃ON₂Cl requires N, 8.74 per cent).

6-Chloro-1 : 4- α -naphthapyrone.—Hydroxymethylene-2-aceto-4-chloro-1-naphthol (1 g.) was refluxed for 3 hours with sulphuric acid (d 1.84, 6 c.c.). The precipitate obtained on adding water to the alcoholic solution was crystallised twice from rectified spirit, m.p. 170-71°. (Found : C, 67.41; H, 3.35. C₁₃H₇O₂ Cl requires C, 67.69; H, 3.04 per cent).

4-Chloro-2-propio-1-naphthol.—4-Chloro-1-naphthol (5 g.) and propionyl chloride (4.6 g.) were heated on a water-bath till there was no evolution of hydrochloric acid gas. Powdered aluminium chloride (7 g.) was added to the crude propionyl chloronaphthol and the mixture heated on a water-bath for 1½ hours. The cold mass was treated with powdered ice and the mixture heated on the water-bath for 1 hour with concentrated hydrochloric acid. The product was collected, washed with water and crystallised from rectified spirit as greenish

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needles, m.p. 90-91°, yield 4 g. It gives in alcoholic solution a deep green colour with ferric chloride. With caustic soda solution it forms an insoluble sodium salt and dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a reddish-brown colour. (Found : Cl, 15.29. $C_{13}H_{11}O_2Cl$ requires Cl, 15.14 per cent).

The *semicarbazone*, crystallised from rectified spirit, did not melt up to 275°. (Found : N, 14.52. $C_{14}H_{14}O_2N_3Cl$ requires N, 14.41 per cent).

6-Chloro-2 : 3-dimethyl-1 : 4- $\alpha\beta$ -naphthapyrone.—4-Chloro-2-propio-1-naphthol (2 g.), acetic anhydride (8.5 g.) and sodium acetate (3.5 g.) was heated at 130-40° for 1½ hours and then at 160-70° for 6 hours. The product, isolated in the usual manner, crystallised from dilute acetic acid (charcoal) as light yellow needles, m.p. 182-83°, mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of 6-chloro-2 : 3-dimethyl-1 : 4- $\alpha\beta$ -naphthapyrone, obtained by the condensation of 4-chloro-1-naphthol with methyl-acetoacetic ester in presence of phosphorus pentoxide (Chakravarti and Bagchi, *loc. cit.*).

The precipitate, obtained by adding water to acetic acid mother-liquor, was subjected to repeated crystallisations but no other product could be isolated.

The *benzylidene* derivative, prepared by condensation with benzaldehyde in presence of alcoholic sodium ethoxide, melted at 189-90° and is identical with that prepared from 6-chloro-2 : 3-dimethyl-1 : 4- $\alpha\beta$ -naphthapyrone.

6-Chloro-3-methyl-4-ethyl-1 : 2- $\alpha\beta$ -naphthapyrone was prepared by heating 4-chloro-2-propio-1-naphthol (2 g.), propionic anhydride (6 g.) and sodium propionate (2.5 g.) at 130-40° for 1 hour and at 190° for 7 hours. The product, isolated in the usual manner, crystallised from alcohol (charcoal) as light yellow needles, m.p. 158-60°. No other product could be isolated. (Found : Cl, 12.76. $C_{16}H_{13}O_2Cl$ requires Cl, 13.02 per cent).

Attempts to condense the above compound with benzaldehyde to form the styryl derivative were unsuccessful.

4-Bromo-2-aceto-1-naphthol.—Powdered aluminium chloride (7 g.) was added to acetyl 4-bromo-1-naphthol, obtained from 4-bromo-1-naphthol (5 g.) and acetyl chloride (3 g.), and the mixture heated on a water-bath for 1 hour. The mixture was then treated with ice and heated on the water-bath with concentrated hydrochloric acid. The solid was collected, washed with water and crystallised from rectified spirit (charcoal) as greenish needles, m.p. 126-27°, mixed m.p. with

the compound prepared by Torry (*loc. cit.*) by bromination of 2-aceto-1-naphthol. (Found : Br, 29.97. Calc. for $C_{12}H_9O_2Br$: Br, 30.19 per cent).

The *benzylidene* derivative, obtained by the condensation of the above ketone with benzaldehyde, crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 176-77° (*cf. Torry, loc. cit.*).

Hydroxymethylene-4-bromo-2-aceto-1-naphthol, prepared from 4-bromo-2-aceto-1-naphthol (2.5 g.), formic ester (5 c.c.) and molecular sodium (1.2 g.) in dry ether (30 c.c.), crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 147-48°. It gives a green precipitate with copper acetate solution. (Found : Br, 26.76. $C_{13}H_9O_3Br$ requires Br, 27.30 per cent).

1-Phenyl-3-(4'-bromo-1'-oxy)-β-naphthylpyrazole, obtained by heating the above hydroxymethylene ketone with phenylhydrazine in glacial acetic acid solution, crystallised from alcohol (charcoal) as a yellow substance, m.p. 180-81°. (Found : N, 7.94. $C_{19}H_{13}ON_2Br$ requires N, 7.67 per cent).

Chalkones from 2-Aceto-4-chloro-1-naphthol.

Benzylidene-2-aceto-4-chloro-1-naphthol.—A solution of 4-chloro-2-aceto-1-naphthol (0.5 g.) in absolute alcohol was condensed with benzaldehyde (1 c.c.) in the presence of sodium ethoxide solution (0.2 g. of sodium in 25 c.c. of absolute alcohol) by heating on the water-bath for 20 minutes. The solution was diluted with water and the red precipitate was collected, washed with water and crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m. p. 186-87°. (Found : Cl, 11.0. $C_{19}H_{13}O_2Cl$ requires Cl, 11.50 per cent).

4'-Methoxy-benzylidene-2-aceto-4-chloro-1-naphthol, obtained by the condensation of 4-chloro-2-aceto-1-naphthol and anisaldehyde, crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m. p. 196-98°. (Found : Cl, 10.51. $C_{20}H_{15}O_3Cl$ requires Cl, 10.49 per cent).

3':4'-Dimethoxybenzylidene-2-aceto-4-chloro-1-naphthol, the condensation product of 2-aceto-4-chloro-1-naphthol and veratric aldehyde, crystallised from dilute acetic acid, m. p. 174-76°. (Found : Cl, 10.10. $C_{21}H_{17}O_4Cl$ requires Cl, 9.63 per cent).